

SPIRITUAL RENEWAL ON THE BASE OF NATIONAL AND RELIGIOUS VALUES IN THE NEW UZBEKISTAN IS A NECESSARY FACTOR OF SOCIAL DEVELOPMENT

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Abstract: In the article, the search for optimal ways of rapid development of socio-economic processes in Uzbekistan, as well as the development of issues such as the preservation of material and spiritual values and their transmission to the next generation, the study of the content and essence of national and religious values are extensively analyzed in the article.

Key words: national value, religion, development, nation, society, spirituality, future

There are theories, teachings, and ideologies that have had a tremendous impact on the development of societies and civilizations. Creative ideas of Zoroaster, Socrates, Plato, Confucius, Alisher Navoi, Mahatma Gandhi and others left an indelible mark in history. Entrepreneur Amir Temur's creative ideas and activities made a great contribution to the rapid development of Eastern culture. The same can be said about German philosophy, which became famous with the names of thinkers such as Kant, Hegel, and Nietzsche. In particular, Hegel's philosophy, which has real national characteristics, rose to the level of the state ideology of the Prussian monarchy, which separated from the Austrian Empire and followed the path of independence.

The secular roots of national-spirituality consist of a set of political, economic, and cultural relations specific to the enlightened world. Over the centuries, humanity has gradually moved towards secularism. Universally recognized principles and features such as the rule of law, political pluralism, interethnic harmony, and interreligious tolerance form the basis of a secular society. Human rights and freedoms, including freedom of conscience, are guaranteed by law. The ideology of such a society develops on the basis of the concept that "Secularism is not secularism", that is, it does not deny the role and importance of religion in the life of society.

The religious roots of national spirituality mean that it is inextricably linked with the human mind and spirit, and therefore its ideological roots go back to religious teachings. That is, we see that in many ideologies, the noble ideas mentioned in divine books such as "Psalms", "Torah", "Bible" and "Quran" have been expressed to a certain extent.

The teachings of Confucius and Lao Tzu, who founded the development path of the Chinese people, were also based on religious views. These teachings have been the national ideology of the country for centuries [1].

During the period of strengthening of independence, it is necessary to solve a number of problems and tasks related to the fundamental historical turn in the political, economic, cultural, spiritual, all aspects of the life of the society. Such a huge task and responsibility requires our people to fully understand the process of spiritual renewal on the one hand, and on the other hand to rely on it in building a democratic society. Because it is becoming a factor of national-spiritual renewal, growth and development.

Development will rise to a higher level in conditions where secular and religious ideas enrich each other. A vivid example of this is the times when great intellectuals such as Imam Bukhari and Musa Khorezmi, Imam Motrudi and Abu Rayhan Beruni, Imam Fazzali and Ibn Sina, Imam Termizi and Abu Nasr Farabi lived and worked.

The dialectic of the struggle between goodness and evil, creativity and destruction has determined the historical forms and essence of national spirituality since time immemorial. That is, contrary to the ideologies of invasion, getting rich at the expense of others, aggression, and fanaticism, the ideas of freedom, independence and justice have continuously emerged and become the victorious flag of the nations.

In the analysis of the issue of moral renewal, the concept of the First President of Uzbekistan I.A. Karimov "Deepening democratic reforms and development of civil society in our country" has not lost its importance. It outlines the following principles of spiritual development:

commitment to universal values;

- strengthening and developing the spiritual heritage of the people;
- free realization of human potential;
- patriotism [2].

At the present time, the Strategy of Actions on the five priority directions of the development of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2017-2021, adopted at the initiative of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev, and the adoption of many decrees and decisions aimed at reforming society, is the program of the renewal process in our country, on the basis of which reforms are being implemented.

The issue of modernization of the society was analyzed as the main issue of the agenda in the pre-election meetings of the President of the Republic of

Uzbekistan. At the meetings, the goal was to achieve radical development, modernization and active participation of the population in the processes of modernization of all sectors of our country, to improve the standard of living of people not only in the city, but also in remote rural areas. Shavkat Mirziyoev spoke about the need to modernize industries, agriculture, technologies, science, culture, and spirituality in Uzbekistan on an innovative basis at meetings with representatives of the voters of each region [3].

Completing such tasks can bring the country to a qualitatively new level and ensure that Uzbekistan enters the ranks of developed countries. It can be seen from the petition that modernization processes in our country will continue on a larger scale based on innovations. In particular, President Sh. Mirziyoev set the task of innovative renewal of the state in the economic sphere. "From this point of view, it is very important to form a program of innovative renewal of the state, to train a new generation of personnel, a new class of investors, who will effectively use innovation and investments. For this, a strong national idea, a national program for the technological development of Uzbekistan and modernization of the domestic market is needed. This program should make it possible to quickly bring Uzbekistan to the ranks of developed countries in the world" [4].

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